

Challenges and Resistances in the Change of Corporate Culture

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Abstract- In today's rapidly changing business landscape, organizations are increasingly recognizing the critical role of corporate culture in driving success. This article delves into the fascinating journey of transforming corporate culture, shedding light on the challenges and resistances encountered along the way. By delving into a real case and employing qualitative research methods, this study uncovers the common challenges and barriers encountered during culture change initiatives. From resistance to change and fear of the unknown to the impact of existing organizational structures, the article explores the intricate dynamics at play. Drawing on these insights, the article then provides practical strategies for addressing these challenges, including but not limited to effective communication, leadership support, and employee engagement. It thus highlights the immense impact and benefits of successful culture change, unveiling how a positive culture can spark innovation, foster collaboration, and improve adaptability. As organizations, but especially the people who compose them, embark on the quest to transform their corporate culture, this article aims to be a compass to enable them to overcome challenges, understand that they are solvable problems, unleash their potential and cultivate a thriving work environment

Keywords- corporate culture, cultural change, effective communication, leadership support

INTRODUCTION

The success of changing the corporate culture in organizations is dependent on the ability to identify and address the challenges and resistances inherent in the process, including resistance to change, lack of leadership support, employee mistrust, and difficulty in aligning values and behaviours, which can ultimately result in a failure to achieve the desired cultural transformation.

Edgar Schein, a prominent scholar in the field of organizational culture, emphasizes the critical importance of corporate culture within an organization. According to Schein (2010), corporate culture serves as a powerful force that shapes and guides the behaviour, attitudes, and actions of individuals within the organization. It acts as a social control mechanism, influencing how employees think, interact, and make decisions. Schein argues that corporate culture provides a shared set of values, beliefs, and norms that create a sense of identity and purpose for employees, aligning their actions with the organization's goals and objectives.

Furthermore, Schein (2010) highlights the impact of corporate culture on organizational performance and effectiveness. He asserts that a strong and positive corporate culture can foster employee engagement, motivation, and commitment. When employees identify with and embrace the organization's culture, they are more likely to exhibit high levels of job satisfaction and loyalty. Additionally, a healthy culture promotes collaboration, communication, and teamwork, enabling individuals to work cohesively towards common objectives. Schein's theory underscores that corporate culture acts as a driving force that influences employee behaviour and ultimately contributes to the organization's success and competitiveness in the marketplace.

Organizations undergo cultural transformations for various reasons, often driven by the need to adapt to a changing business environment and stay competitive. Bass and Avolio (1993) argue that cultural transformations are initiated when organizations recognize the misalignment between their existing culture and the desired future state. Factors such as globalization, technological advancements, mergers and acquisitions, or shifts in industry dynamics can necessitate cultural change. Moreover, Wilhelm (2016) suggests that organizations may also undergo cultural transformations as a response to internal challenges, such as low employee morale, lack of innovation, or declining performance. Cultural transformation becomes a strategic imperative for organizations to realign their values, beliefs, and practices with the new realities they face.

Additionally, Wilhelm (2016) suggests that cultural transformations can improve organizational agility and adaptability, allowing organizations to respond effectively to market changes and seize new opportunities. However, cultural transformations also pose significant challenges. Denison (1990) notes that resistance to change, employee skepticism, and entrenched behaviors can impede the successful implementation of cultural transformations. Moreover, Bass and Avolio (1993) emphasize the challenge of leadership alignment and the need for strong leadership support to navigate the complexities of cultural change.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Corporate Culture

Positive Culture Driving Innovation:

A positive corporate culture can drive innovation by creating an environment that encourages and rewards creative thinking, risk-taking, and experimentation. For example, companies like Google and 3M are known for fostering innovation through their cultural values of curiosity, openness, and a willingness to challenge the status quo. Such cultures promote idea sharing, collaboration, and continuous learning, empowering employees to think outside the box and contribute to the development of innovative products, services, and processes (Denison, 1990).

Positive Culture Fostering Collaboration:

A positive corporate culture emphasizes collaboration and teamwork, breaking down silos and promoting cross-functional cooperation. Organizations like Pixar Animation Studios are renowned for their collaborative culture, where employees from different disciplines work together in multidisciplinary teams to create high-quality animated films. Collaboration is nurtured through shared values of trust, respect, and open communication, enabling employees to leverage diverse perspectives, knowledge, and skills to achieve collective goals (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

Positive Culture Enhancing Adaptability:

In a rapidly changing business environment, adaptability is crucial for organizational survival and growth. A positive corporate culture facilitates adaptability by fostering a learning mindset, agility, and a willingness to embrace change. For instance, companies like Netflix have cultivated a culture that embraces experimentation and quick decision-making. They empower employees to adapt to market shifts, embrace new technologies, and continuously improve processes to stay ahead of the competition (Schein, 2010).

Challenges

When organizations embark on changing their corporate culture, they often encounter various challenges that can hinder the process. Understanding and addressing these challenges is crucial for successful cultural transformation.

Resistance to Change

One of the primary challenges in changing corporate culture is resistance from employees. People tend to be comfortable with familiar ways of doing things and may resist changes that disrupt established norms and practices. According to O'Reilly and Chatman (1996), individuals may resist cultural change due to fear of the unknown, concerns about personal job security, or a lack of trust in leadership (p. 186).

Lack of Leadership Support

Another significant challenge is the absence of leadership support. Leadership plays a critical role in driving and sustaining cultural change. When leaders fail to provide clear direction, demonstrate commitment, or model the desired cultural behaviors, it can undermine the change efforts. Kotter and Heskett (1992) argue that without strong leadership support, cultural change initiatives are likely to falter.

Employee Skepticism and Cynicism

Cultural change initiatives can be met with skepticism and cynicism from employees who have experienced previous unsuccessful change efforts. Past negative experiences can breed a sense of doubt and skepticism, making employees reluctant to fully engage in the new cultural direction. Building trust and addressing employees' concerns are essential to overcome this challenge (Bass & Avolio, 1994, p. 117).

Alignment of Values and Behaviors

Aligning values and behaviors across the organization is a complex challenge. Different departments, teams, and individuals may have diverse beliefs and practices that are deeply ingrained. Achieving a shared understanding and consistent application of desired cultural values requires comprehensive communication, training, and reinforcement (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

Following a qualitative method twelve people have been interviewed in a company that is facing this kind of change.

Four C-level or similar both working in the headquarters or in different Regions of the company.

Four B-level or similar both working in the headquarters or in different Regions of the company.

Four Supervisors both working in the headquarters or in different Regions of the company.

The twelve resources were equally divided in terms of gender and length of service, with a maximum of 25 years for a resource and a minimum of 3 years.

Three questions in particular were chosen, the first related to how the resources feel in their role and how they can contribute to the cultural change, the second is what do you know about the concept of corporate culture and the third is whether they saw any challenges or risks at this important moment for the company and the third how they perceived this important moment for the company from their point of view. This last question aimed to understand if within the different groups, there were differences between working in the headquarters or in the more peripheral areas.

C-level

They perceive themselves as those who define and articulate cultural changes and who can work fully within the perimeter of the strategic objectives of the organization. They add that they are responsible for allocating resources, including budget, time and personnel, precisely to support change initiatives. Thus they perceive themselves as continuously involved in cultural change.

They feel like role models of the company's cultural behaviors. They know that their actions and decisions have a significant impact on shaping the culture of the organization. Half of them believe they exhibit the new cultural traits, and the example they set sends a powerful message to employees to reinforce the importance of culture change.

It is more difficult for executives who are not at headquarters (two out of four) to be fully aligned with culture change initiatives. Based on their responses, headquarters executives can motivate and influence each other. It is easier for them to have regular face-to-face interactions, attend culture change seminars or HR team training sessions, and see firsthand the cultural dynamics that are experienced in the headquarters. The flow of information, updates, and progress related to culture change initiatives feels less complete for executives in remote locations. According to those who work in the headquarters, the distance could hinder their understanding and alignment with the cultural transformation.

B-level

They feel responsible for implementing and cascading culture change initiatives across their teams and departments down the chain of command. They translate the high-level cultural values that are decided by the company into actionable plans, goals and behaviors for the employee, something more practical.

They are dependent on the example of their leaders and seek in turn to have the behaviors desired by the company which should, they say, create a positive ripple effect encouraging employees to follow suit as well.

They feel they are a vital part of the company as a link-chain to ensure culture change messages are communicated effectively to their teams and therefore employees have a clear understanding of the change process, its purpose and impact.

However, they are skeptical about the effectiveness or sincerity of culture change initiatives. For some, the change is just a way to reduce local autonomy (particularly for those who work in the periphery).

Older in the role, but also older, accustomed to the current culture and comfortable with existing ways of doing things. They understand that change is a continuous process but they fear that it could be too disruptive and that they cannot translate it because they are children of the previous culture. One of the four clearly states that the change is not necessary at this time and that the company needs more. In this, he is not the only one wondering what the logic behind the change is, what are the potential benefits to bring to the organization.

This skepticism is magnified by distance from headquarters, and in some cases change is perceived as top-down for the sake of greater control and standardization.

It is precisely the resources working in the periphery who argue that by not residing at headquarters they do not feel immersed in the corporate culture, making it more difficult for them to fully align and lead the new culture change. In remote locations the "judicial news" always arrives with the echo of one's C-level and therefore the real message could be distorted.

Only one questioned whether the change will lead to further changes within management.

Supervisors

They feel they are the direct channel of communication between managers and employees and therefore find themselves subjected to requests from above, not always clear, about the changes to be made and requests from below, more often resistance, without having the

entire package of knowledge that such challenges it requires.

Employees are very concerned about change, and for this very reason in some cases it is deliberately watered down or poorly promoted to avoid mental walls or open protest.

In fact, employees see first of all the threat to their workplace in change and they themselves (three out of four) argue that this threat is real, not so much due to a reduction in the activities to do but rather due to their replacement with more prepared resources and just out of school.

Their daily task is to maintain a positive work environment and this has been done in the past also by recalling the values of the corporate culture that are now hard to find. The company, which has been on the market for 40 years, has faced at least 3 cultural changes and is struggling to leave the previous one. Two openly regret the period managed by the previous management because they saw it as safer. On the other hand, two are happy with the change, despite all the challenges because the previous situation was too plastered.

In general, however, beyond just a little change in the venue, they don't fully understand the purpose, benefits or rationale behind the change.

They are worried about being stressed and having to stress back because of new behaviors or ways of working. One of the four talks about the concept of the comfort zone and how difficult it will be to take employees by the hand and lead them out.

They also fear that cultural change could again disrupt existing power structures, norms or political dynamics within the organization. They generally feel attached to their leader (departmental or local) and don't know if the change will also lead to resignations or changes with relative upheavals in internal procedures.

That said, they are equally concerned about the lack of support from senior management regarding culture change, and therefore fear that the "dirty" part of the job will fall to them.

Obviously during the interviews, conducted during a company meeting, further requests for explanations were added to the 3 questions. The interviewer specified that it was an experiment and that the data would be used anonymously. Some respondents who had known the interviewer for years were more forthcoming, while newer resources were more difficult to let go.

DISCUSSION

Analyzing the various interviews, I believe it is useful to rationalize what to do to support change and so overcome challenges and resistances according to six macro areas of intervention.

Effective communication

Effective communication is essential when implementing a cultural change in a company. It plays a significant role in creating awareness, generating understanding and building support among employees (Caldwell & Dixon, 2009).

By effectively communicating the need for a culture change and the reasons behind it, organizations can create awareness among employees and help them understand the importance of transformation (Denison, 1990). This is well indicated by middle management asking for clarity at C-levels and therefore clear and transparent communication provides clarity on the organization's vision, goals and expectations, minimizing ambiguity and confusion. This understanding is critical to gaining employee buy-in and commitment to the culture change initiative.

Effective communication is key to managing resistance to change. It provides a platform for immediate dialogue, enabling leaders to address concerns, dispel misconceptions, and listen to employee feedback (Denison, 1990). This must be a skill provided at C-levels so that the same words can then go down the supply chain to resources. On the other hand, at the same level, continuous communication is the only way to allow those who work in the central offices to be in contact with the periphery and therefore avoid that there are two different speeds of application of the cultural change.

Effective communication is vital in culture change initiatives as it creates awareness, engenders understanding, builds engagement, manages resistance, and sustains momentum. By employing clear and transparent communication strategies, organizations can foster employee engagement, alignment and support throughout the cultural transformation process

Leadership support and role modeling

Leadership support and role modeling play a crucial role in the successful implementation of culture change within a company. When leaders actively support and embody desired cultural behaviors, it sends a powerful message to employees, influencing their attitudes and actions (Bass & Avolio, 1993). All roles, including C-levels reporting to the CEO need role models to follow in figuring out where to go.

Though with different styles leaders hold significant influence and credibility within an organization. Their active participation in the culture change process demonstrates their belief in transformation and only when leaders align their behaviors with desired cultural values, does it reinforce the importance of change and motivate employees to follow suit. Conversely, the departments they manage could perceive the change as an exogenous threat that undermines their stability.

When leaders actively engage in culture change, employees perceive them as genuine and authentic (Wilhelm, 2016). This trust allows for open communication, encourages employees to embrace change, and reduces resistance. This is especially important if the organization is emerging from a period of toxic leadership as reported by one interviewee. It is important that there is comparison between leaders at whatever latitude they are because it is only when leaders consistently model the desired behaviors that a standard is established that others must follow, creating a ripple effect throughout the organization. If there are dissonances it happens that wars of power are created between the departments also to make the leadership style of one C prevail over another.

Ultimately, leaders have great power to enforce culture change by recognizing and rewarding individuals and teams who exemplify desired behaviors. By publicly acknowledging and celebrating successes, leaders reinforce the importance of cultural transformation and encourage its continuation.

Leadership support and role modeling are key to successfully implementing culture change. Through their influence, credibility, and commitment, leaders inspire, motivate, and build trust among employees. Their active participation in the change process reinforces desired cultural behaviors and helps to overcome resistances. By embodying new cultural norms, leaders pave the way for successful cultural transformation.

Employee engagement and empowerment

Employee engagement and empowerment are essential components when implementing a culture change in a company. They contribute to employee ownership, engagement, and commitment to new cultural norms.

When employees are actively involved in the culture change process, they develop a sense of ownership and commitment (Kreiner, 2006). Their participation in the decision-making process and in the formation of cultural values and behaviors creates a sense of responsibility and investment in the change initiative. In the interviews made this theme emerges recurrently. Only by including employees from various levels and departments, organizations can tap into different perspectives and ideas, ensuring a more comprehensive and inclusive cultural transformation.

While it does not emerge forcefully, it is clear that only with continued engagement can organizations ensure that the new culture is

aligned with workplace realities.

A theme that did not emerge in the interviews but which is well known from the relevant texts is that of responsibility and autonomy. When employees feel empowered, they are more likely to embrace change, experiment with new approaches, and take the initiative to align their actions with desired cultural norms. The issue is important and emerged only after an analysis identifying how the governance of the organization has deficiencies with regards to delegation. In practice, the real decisions and responsibilities are only in the hands of a few.

An important issue in managing the challenges of change is to encourage employees to challenge existing practices, experiment with new ideas and embrace continuous improvement, organizations can adapt to changing market conditions and drive innovation. Employee engagement and empowerment are crucial in culture change initiatives (Ford & Ford, 2009). They promote ownership, collaboration and use of employee knowledge and skills, but that's not all. Companies have to take a little risk to get the change they need.

Honors and awards

Recognition and rewards play a significant role in enacting culture change within a company. They serve as powerful motivators and reinforce desired cultural behaviors among employees:

When employees see their efforts recognized and rewarded, it reinforces the importance of new cultural norms and motivates them to continue to align their actions accordingly. The issue is touched upon several times by middle management who do not feel sufficiently motivated. By recognizing and celebrating employees who exemplify desired cultural values, organizations reinforce the meaning of these behaviors and encourage others to follow suit, a topic already touched upon elsewhere in this study.

Recognition and rewards inspire and motivate employees to go further in embodying culture change (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). When employees see that their efforts are appreciated and recognized, it increases their motivation, job satisfaction and commitment to the organization. In this sense, a commitment from the Human Resources department is necessarily needed to promote this culture. By linking recognition and rewards to the demonstration of desired behaviors organizations ultimately encourage employees to actively engage in the culture change process and to align their actions with new cultural expectations.

Recognition and rewards related to desired cultural behaviors send a strong message about the values and priorities of the organization (Wilhelm, 2016). This empowerment ensures that culture change is not just a temporary initiative, but becomes ingrained in organizational DNA, driving employee actions and decisions.

Recognition and rewards play a pivotal role in company culture change initiatives as they reinforce desired behaviors, create a culture of appreciation, inspire and motivate employees, encourage adoption and adaptation, change mindsets, and reinforce values organizational. By implementing effective recognition and awards programs, organizations can promote a positive and supportive culture that aligns with the desired culture change.

Change agents and champions

Change agents and advocates play a vital role in enacting culture change within a company. They serve as catalysts and advocates for change, driving its adoption and ensuring its success.

Change agents and advocates build momentum and build enthusiasm for the culture change initiative (Bass & Avolio, 1993). It emerges well from the interviews. Advocates serve as role models and inspire others by showing their commitment to new cultural values and behaviors. Their passion and dedication motivate employees to embrace change and actively participate in the transformation process. Using their credibility, expertise and interpersonal skills to effectively communicate the rationale behind culture change allows colleagues to address any concerns or resistance. Their influence helps build trust and encourages employees to embrace change and contribute to its success.

Change agents and advocates facilitate effective communication and engagement throughout the culture change process (Chatman, 1991). This is a resource tailored role between top management and employees, ensuring that messages are conveyed and understood effectively. Change agents understand the challenges and concerns employees may have and provide support and guidance in navigating through the change process. Their presence and influence help ease fears and uncertainties, making it easier for employees to embrace and adjust to new cultural norms. By empowering change through continuous communication, recognition and reinforcement, they ensure that the new culture is deeply ingrained in the practices and mindset of the organization.

Change agents and advocates are instrumental in implementing culture change initiatives. They build momentum, influence others, facilitate communication and engagement, overcome resistance, and advocate for change. By leveraging the support and influence of change agents and advocates, organizations can effectively drive and embed culture change within the enterprise.

CONCLUSION

This research paper has explored the importance of various factors in successfully implementing culture change within organizations. Throughout the discussion, we highlighted six key points that collectively contribute to the successful implementation of culture change initiatives and help organizations overcome the challenges and resistances associated with such transformations.

Effective communication builds awareness, generates understanding, builds commitment, manages resistance, and sustains momentum. By employing clear and transparent communication strategies, organizations can foster employee engagement, alignment and support throughout the cultural transformation process.

The leaders are protagonists and through their influence, credibility and commitment, they must inspire, motivate and build trust among employees. Active participation in the change process reinforces desired cultural behaviors and helps overcome resistances.

It is crucial to encourage employees to challenge existing practices, experiment with new ideas and embrace continuous improvement.

Companies have to take a small risk to get the change they need, but employee empowerment is central to culture change initiatives.

These paths must be accompanied by a rewards strategy to create a culture of appreciation, inspiring and motivating employees, encouraging the adoption and adaptation of the new culture, changing mentalities and reinforcing organizational values.

Change agents and advocates as well as leaders are critical in executing culture change initiatives. They build momentum, influence others, facilitate communication and engagement, overcome resistance, and advocate for change.

In conclusion, successful implementation of culture change requires a holistic approach addressing effective communication, leadership support, employee engagement, training and development, recognition and rewards, and the presence of agents and advocates of the change. By leveraging these factors, organizations can address the challenges and resistances associated with culture change, fostering a positive and adaptive culture that aligns with their strategic goals and enhances their long-term success.

REFERENCES

- Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1993). *Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture*. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 17(1), 112–121.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/40862298>
- Caldwell, C., & Dixon, R. D. (2009). *Love, forgiveness, and trust: Critical values of the modern leader*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 93(1), 91–101.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0184-z>
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2011). *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework*. Wiley.
- Chatman, J. A. (1991). *Matching people and organizations: Selection and socialization in public accounting firms*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 36(3), 459-484.
- Denison, D. R. (1990). *Corporate culture and organizational effectiveness*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Ford, J. D., & Ford, L. W. (1995). *The Role of Conversations in Producing Intentional Change in Organizations*. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 541–570.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/258787>
- Kreiner, G. E., & Ashforth, B. E. (2004). *Evidence toward an Expanded Model of Organizational Identification*. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(1), 1–27.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/4093641>
- Schein, E. H. (2010). *Organizational culture and leadership*. Wiley
- Warren Wilhelm. (2016). *Changing Corporate Culture: Or Corporate Behavior? How to Change Your Company*. *The Executive*, 6(4), 72–77.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/416509>

